

Experiences from NASA/Langley's DMSS Project

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Abstract

There is a trend in institutions with high-performance computing and data management requirements to explore mass storage systems with peripherals directly attached to a high-speed network. The Distributed Mass Storage System (DMSS) Project at the NASA Langley Research Center (LaRC) has placed such a system into production use. This paper describes the DMSS system and relates experiences from production use.

Introduction

The DMSS project has integrated emerging technologies from the areas of data storage hardware, high-speed communications, and hierarchical storage management software into the latest production mass storage system to serve LaRC. This new system is characterized by peripherals directly attached to a high-speed network, and a workstation acting as the file server. The file server no longer handles data a high-speed data transfers involving high-speed clients like a CRAY Y-MP. Between 1991 and 1993 LaRC assembled and developed a prototype of this system as a proof of concept [1]. From the end of 1993 until the start of production (October 1994) LaRC concentrated on system stability issues.

DMSS is responsible for meeting the mass storage needs of the central scientific computing complex as well as the distributed computing systems spread over the local area network. It replaced the previous storage system, which was run on the CRAY Y-MP using the Data Migration Facility (DMF) software.

DMSS design goals

The first design goal for DMSS was to provide a cost-effective storage solution to replace the CRAY Y-MP implementation. Previous solutions to mass storage problems incorporated a supercomputer or mini-supercomputer as the file server in order to meet performance needs. Machines of these classes are expensive to buy and maintain.

The separation of data and control as spelled out in the Mass Storage System Reference Model Version 4 [2] was a good way to achieve performance while reducing the throughput capacity needed on the server. Using network-attached peripherals has allowed the DMSS file server to become a workstation-class machine costing less than 100 thousand dollars rather than a mini-supercomputer-class machine costing over one million dollars.

The second goal was that the solution be an open systems solution so that it could provide an environment for evolvability when new technologies surface. Wherever possible, platforms that adhered to standards were chosen.

The third goal was high availability. Due to the limited disk space on the supercomputers, user jobs rely on the mass storage system for the retrieval of required files before running, and the storage of restart files and result files at the end of jobs. Thousands of workstations and PCs on the local area network also depend on the mass storage system for data sharing, system backup, and postprocessing of supercomputer runs. System redundancy was provided in many system components in order to increase availability.

The fourth goal was to maximize the performance for supercomputer accesses. We achieved this via the Intelligent Peripheral Interface 3 (IPI3) [3] third-party transfer protocol [4] over a High Performance Parallel Interface (HIPPI) ([5],[6]) switch control [7] fabric.

The fifth goal was scalability. The solution must be easily expandable, should the requirements for mass storage change drastically within a short time. DMSS has removed the limitations of many of the current storage systems, such as limits on the types and amount of devices that can be attached and utilized.

The five goals mentioned above are by no means mutually exclusive. The cost of workstation-class file servers enables the provision of file server redundancy in a cost-effective manner. Network-attached peripherals allow for expandability and high-performance access from HIPPI-attached supercomputers. Openness, evolvability, expandability, and scalability all translate into savings on capital equipment and human resources.

Figure 1. DMSS configuration

Implementation

DMSS configuration

Figure 1 shows the DMSS configuration. DMSS has two file servers, one IBM RS6000/990 and one IBM RS6000/970, that have 256 Megabytes (MB) of memory each. The 990 is the primary server and the 970 is the secondary server. The National Storage Laboratory (NSL)/UniTree, a distributed hierarchical storage-management software package marketed by IBM, runs on the servers. NSL/UniTree is a version of UniTree that has additional features of multiple storage hierarchies and support for IPI3 third-party transfer drivers. NSL/UniTree manages two IBM 9570 disk array systems totaling 140 gigabytes (GB) and 14.4 terabytes (TB) of magnetic tape storage in three silos of the StorageTek Automated Cartridge System (ACS 4490). The HIPPI-attached disk array systems and STK 4490 are accessible to both file servers. The STK 4490 access to the IBM RS6000 is via block mux. When DMSS first went into production, the two file servers, two disk array systems, and the CRAY Y-MP and CRAY 2 were all connected to a Network System Corporation (NSC) PS-32 HIPPI switch, which allows the simultaneous communication of 32 devices or computers, each at 100 MB/sec rate. The CRAY 2 has since been decommissioned and thus not included in the present DMSS.

In addition to the HIPPI-IPI3 disk array systems, each server also has 16 GB of SCSI disks, which store the NSL/UniTree databases. An external SCSI disk system, which can be attached to either the primary or secondary server, contains the primary copies of the databases. The

purpose of this disk system is to facilitate the switchover from one server to another.

CRAY HIPPI/IPI3 third-party drivers

LaRC has developed kernel drivers to perform HIPPI/IPI3 third-party transfers on both of the CRAY Y-MP and CRAY 2. These drivers act as Movers as specified in the Mass Storage Reference Model Version 5 [8]. The drivers were first developed under the CRAY operating system UNICOS Release 7 and have been in production use. Currently, the CRAY Y-MP driver is being ported onto the UNICOS Release 8 platform. LaRC undertook the driver development because CRAY Research (CRI) indicated that it had no plans for such a product. CRI still does not support a third-party driver. The driver has both a kernel version and user-space version. The user-space version can easily be maintained without costly supercomputer system time, but its concurrent third-party transfers are less efficient.

Access to DMSS

There are three different ways for the users to transfer files to/from DMSS: ftp, rcp, and the Explicit Archival and Retrieval System (EARS). The majority of accesses use either EARS or rcp. NFS is not used because of very poor performance.

Clients with HIPPI connections use third-party transfers to transfer data directly to/from the HIPPI attached disk arrays. Clients without HIPPI get their data through the server.

FTP. NSL/UniTree supplies a special ftpd that communicates directly with NSL/UniTree when I/O is done and talks to clients using standard ftp protocol. Therefore, no modification is necessary at the ftp client-side in order to transfer data to/from NSL/UniTree.

RCP. LaRC has modified rcp on the file server to act like the special ftpd. All I/O to the local machine has been replaced with the appropriate calls from the NSL/UniTree client API library (libnsl) to effect I/O directly with NSL/UniTree. A client's rcp still uses the standard rcp communications, so no client-side modification is necessary.

EARS. EARS is an interface that LaRC has been using for years. Originally it was part of our MVS-based mass storage system. EARS provides a UNIX-like set of commands for access to DMSS (that is, masls, maschmod, masrm, masput, masget, and so on). On the server these commands are C programs, which are linked with libnsl in order to communicate directly with NSL/UniTree.

On most clients the EARS commands are simple shell scripts which pass along the command they want to run to the server for execution. The exceptions are masput and masget, which normally invoke rcp on the client (which then talks to the modified rcp on the server).

On clients with HIPPI connections masput and masget are the same C programs that exist on the server. This allows these clients to use the third-party transfers to dramatically increase throughput.

DMF to NSL/UniTree transition

LaRC developed a mechanism for transparently transitioning over 1.7 million files from DMF to NSL/UniTree without having to move all of the data before the switchover to DMSS. The design consists of four parts:

- DMF database extraction and UniTree population
- Modified tapesrvr/mvr code
- Mount-and-Read (MNR) task
- A background transition program (plowd)

DMF database extraction and UniTree population. Software was developed that traverses the DMF databases and the UNICOS file system and generates all of the information needed to find a DMF file. This data is then passed to a population program that makes the appropriate entries into the NSL/UniTree databases.

Modified NSL/UniTree server code. Once the population is finished, a second set of tape server processes (called dmfsrvr and dmfmovr) are started; they deal with the new entries. The dmfsrvr is the same code as the normal

NSL/UniTree tape server. A few things were changed such as disabling writes to the dmfsrvr. The main changes occur in the read logic. The new flow is as follows:

```
Get file header
while not done
    Determine the next tape the data is on
    Call MNR (see next section)
    Tell mover to move data
    Update MNR cache info
    go back to top of loop if not done
```

The dmfmovr does not actually get data off a tape. The MNR process (described in the next section) gets the data off tape and creates a disk image of the tape. The dmfmovr reads this disk image to get the data to send to the disk mover. The mover code has been changed to do this.

Mount and read (MNR) process. This program understands how to handle a DMF tape. When the dmfsrvr gets a request for a file, it invokes MNR. MNR then mounts and reads the tape and creates a disk image of the tape. It then parses the image to create an index of DMF files and offsets. It then passes the offset and length back to the dmfsrvr, which is in turn passed to the dmfmovr.

MNR maintains a cache of these tape images. If a user makes a request for a file which is on a tape that is already on disk, then the response is almost immediate. MNR is responsible for managing the cache of images. We chose to cache the tape image to disk in order to minimize the number of tape mounts and tape positioning needed to transition all of the data into NSL/UniTree.

PLOWD. The dmfsrvr/dmfmovr and MNR will handle each individual user's request for a DMF format file. The first time a DMF file is accessed via NSL/UniTree it is moved to the disk server. Once there, it will be re-migrated to a new tape in the NSL/UniTree format. We want to have all old DMF files converted some day; however, the users will never request all of the old files. A program called plowd is responsible for eventually accessing all of the files. Plowd constantly looks at the tape image cache from MNR. When a new tape comes into the cache, it scans the database to determine what files are on that tape and then issues a stage request on those files (one at a time). These requests go through the dmfsrvr just as if the user had requested the file. The dmfsrvr then calls MNR, which finds the tape image already on disk, and so it responds quickly.

If the system is idle, plowd will start the process by itself, making requests for files, causing a tape to be cached to disk. Due to this activity NSL/UniTree has never been idle since it went into production.

As of 16 January 1995, 53 percent of the files and 70 percent of the data have be "plowed." The entire process takes approximately six months.

Miscellaneous NSL/UniTree enhancements

NSL/UniTree is lacking in the area of system management tools. Many functions we had taken for granted in other systems were not available in NSL/UniTree. For instance, we could not tell which files resided on which tapes, nor could we produce a report of how much data was stored in the system (other than doing a `ls -lR` of everything, which takes five days). LaRC has written a number of tools to try and fill the gaps in the NSL/UniTree supplied utilities. These utilities allow LaRC to examine the NSL/UniTree databases, either to investigate problems or produce usage reports.

Since all access methods to DMSS are under our control, we have added many logging statements to `ftp`, `rnp`, and `EARS`. These logging statements give very good and up-to-the minute statistics on system activity and file-transfer traffic.

It is LaRC's intention to give all enhancements and bug fixes to IBM to be incorporated into the NSL/UniTree product. The one modification to NSL/UniTree that LaRC has not passed back to IBM at this point is for lazy tape dismounting. This modification causes the `tapesrvr` to hold off dismounting a tape for 15 seconds in case another request comes for that tape. This helps to reduce the number of tape mounts needed in a day.

Performance and statistics

CRAY Y-MP performance

This section contains performance comparisons of conventional file transfers via TCP/IP (using RCP) and the third-party transfers of whole files between the DMSS's HIPPI/IPI3 disk array systems and the CRAY Y-MP's DD-41 and DD-42 disks (which are not striped).

Single-file transfers between the DMSS and CRAY memory follow the performance curve shown in Figure 2. The third-party transfer rate approaches the first-party rate of 50 MB per second. Read operations from the disk array approach the maximum transfer rate faster than write operations (for example, a 4 MB file can be read at 20 MB per second and be written at 18 MB per second).

Single-file transfers going from DMSS to CRAY disk follow the performance curve shown in Figure 3. Note that the performance of the CRAY disk and buffer cache drastically affect the performance. The files are transferred using 4 MB buffers. Increasing the buffer size beyond 4 MB has

Figure 2. First party vs. third party time.

little effect on performance. For comparison Figure 3 also contains performance figures for CRAY to DMSS performance through RCP over FDDI. The RCP used is the same RCP referred to earlier. This graph illustrates the performance benefits of HIPPI/IPI3 third-party versus standard TCP/IP over FDDI. The aggregate performance of CRAY disk to DMSS transfers can approach the maximum of 50 MB per second (per disk array).

From these statistics, we conclude that, by employing a workstation file server and using third-party transfer, our system has not suffered from poorer performance, but instead has outperformed our previous system. It also validates that the third-party kernel driver can be used to process many requests in parallel, with a significant increase in performance over conventional FTP and RCP transfers. The better performance has provided an increase in CRAY Y-MP system efficiency and job turnaround time.

Migration/staging performance

The system is currently using 3490E tapes with a block mux channel. The implementation of the channel is poor. The best sustained performance observed has been 1.5-2.0 MB per second. The channel never performs more than a 2.0 MB per second aggregate rate. Also, when the channel is active it drains about 40 percent of the CPU. We plan to switch to SCSI STK access later this year.

NSL/UniTree only uses one tape drive when migrating data to tape. This limits the amount of data that can

Figure 3. CRAY Y-MP's DMSS access (disk to disk).

be migrated per day. Currently it can handle a maximum of about 50–75 GB per day. After the switch to SCSI this should increase to about 100 GB daily. The migration performance is currently acceptable for LaRC, but may not be for all sites.

At LaRC, NSL/UniTree has written an average of 510 MB per standard-length 3490 tape and an average of 1086 MB per double-length tape with the STK compression turned on. For noncompressible data, NSL/UniTree gets an average of 437 MB per standard-length tape.

Statistics for file stages from tape are difficult to interpret because there are many variables that affect performance (such as file size, number of available tape drives, proximity of tape to drive, tape length, and so on). Over a two-day period, where adequate tape drives were present for all requests, the following statistics were collected: 291 files were staged from tape with a 134-second average wait-time and a 113-second median wait-time. The longest wait time was 482 seconds (500 MB file).

The lazy tape dismounting modification saved 3,793 tape mounts (19 percent of all mounts for read) for the first three months of operation.

Another measurement LaRC uses to gauge system performance is the hit rate on the disk cache. That is the percentage of file retrieval requests which come directly from disk without needing to be staged from tape. We plan to use this information to determine when we need to expand the disk cache. We currently have a 140 GB cache. This

is big enough to hold one week's worth of the most active files. Unfortunately, the DMF-to-UniTree transition is not complete. This activity severely reduces the cache hit rate. The current average hit rate is about 55 percent. When the transition is over we hope to see this rate rise to 90 percent.

File accessing and manipulation

NSL/UniTree does a poor job when accessing large numbers of files. This has been the biggest complaint from the user community since switching over to NSL/UniTree. The best long-listing performance (masls -l) achieved has been 18 entries listed per second. Short listings (without the -l) achieve almost UNIX speeds. Processes that change file attributes handle only around five to ten entries per second. File removal occurs at only about two per second.

Availability

There are two separate conditions that affect DMSS availability. First, if the server is down, then all access to DMSS is denied and jobs that require DMSS will abort. The second condition is when NSL/UniTree is down, but the server is up. In this case service is not denied but delayed. The EARS, FTP, and RCP programs have built-in logic to retry requests to NSL/UniTree when it is down. These requests will block until NSL/UniTree is reinitialized, at which time they will run to completion. This occurs for processes running when NSL/UniTree is brought down and processes started after the shutdown. This is desirable behavior. We can shut down NSL/UniTree for system backups, problem investigation, or software installation without impacting a running job (except for the delay).

The IBM RS 6000/9XXs have proven to be very reliable machines. Since DMSS was put in production in October 1994, we have had one AIX crash from which we immediately recovered and no occurrences of hardware problems.

Other DMSS components that contribute to the DMSS's high availability are the HIPPI-IPI3 disk array systems and the HIPPI switch. LaRC is pleased with the IBM 9570 disk array systems, which have given the reliability anticipated. We have lost a total of four disks (out of 120) in the previous year. When one disk is lost the array is still available. Reconstruction of the lost disk to a standby disk takes between eight and fifteen minutes. The only serious hardware problem occurred when two unexpected power outages occurred within two hours. We lost two disks at the same time during the first outage, which resulted in data loss (about 70 files that had not made it to tape). IBM has identified the faulty component that caused the failures and will be updating our drives in the spring. The HIPPI switch has not had a problem in the last year.

The 1994 Christmas and 1995 New Year holidays were the first time at LaRC that the whole central complex shut down for six days without interrupting mass storage service for distributed users.

Usage statistics

Overall usage statistics are gathered once per week. The overall usage as of 16 January 1995: There were 1,880,082 files totaling 3.07 TB of space used. The average file size was 1.6 MB and the largest file was 1.9 GB.

Distribution of file sizes:	
0 KB-1 KB:	338,667
1 KB-10 KB:	612,941
10 KB-100 KB:	411,110
100 KB-1 MB:	308,367
1 MB-10 MB:	150,684
10 MB-100 MB:	54,403
100 MB-bigger:	3,903

Weekly data traffic over the prior three months:				
	Files put	GB's put	Files got	GB's got
High	33,618	81.62	17,831	119.17
Median	17,343	58.49	3,539	50.06
Low	9,885	37.20	1,739	22.59

Comparing DMF to NSL/UniTree

This section will make some comparisons between DMF and NSL/UniTree based on our experiences running both in production environments. This paper will not attempt to assign scores to the packages or pick a "winner." Both packages have different strengths and weaknesses.

Migration/recall

A typical migration under DMF involved around four GB of data and ten 3490 tapes (400 MB each). It would finish in about 30 minutes and use all available tape drives. While using all of the drives increased migration speed, it effectively interfered with any file recalls (generally for five to ten minutes). There was an average of three to five migrations per day. Using these numbers we can conclude that DMF could handle a maximum of 192 GB per day. As described earlier, NSL/UniTree will handle a maximum of 100 GB per day (with SCSI 3490E tapes). Both systems are capable of handling our current needs; however, if the average incoming data approached or exceeded the maximum then the system would be unusable.

DMF wasted tape space because it did not make use of compression on the STK drives. DMF was told that the 3490 tapes could hold 400 MB. It never tried to put more than 400 MB on a tape (even though the data was compressed and there was more room). For the same tapes NSL/UniTree averaged 510 MB.

We did not collect recall statistics while using DMF.

DMF

- + Able to migrate more data per day.
- All drives used when migrating, thus causing recall delays.

NSL/UniTree

- Only uses one drive during migration.
- + Fully utilizes tapes.

Operations

DMF is a more mature product from an operations standpoint. The tools that are needed to analyze problems, analyze and fix database consistency, and produce usage and accounting statistics are present in DMF and not in NSL/UniTree. LaRC has written some utilities and has used some unsupported utilities from IBM to help fill the void. Both packages provide a tape-repacking utility. As with the other operational tools, the DMF version was more stable and mature than its NSL/UniTree counterpart.

NSL/UniTree logs are poorly suited for system monitoring and problem analysis. There are too many log files, each with differing formats. The information is cryptic, and in some cases there is too much useless information while in others there is not enough good information. It takes experience to decode the logs and get an idea of what the system is or was doing.

NSL/UniTree can be brought down for extended periods of time for any reason (backups, problem analysis, and such) without causing problems for applications needing NSL/UniTree services. Client programs will block and wait for NSL/UniTree to return to service. Thus, batch jobs and cron processes will not be effected due to an NSL/UniTree outage. Applications needing mass storage files would abort instead of block, if DMF was taken down.

NSL/UniTree lacks code to do an orderly shutdown. Any time it goes down there is a chance for database corruption. We have had one such instance since DMSS went into production.

While NSL/UniTree does not provide back-up utilities for its databases (except the tape server) it has proven to be easier and faster to back up. We typically back up the databases once a night by writing them to the disk array. NSL/UniTree is down while this happens. It takes approximately 30 minutes to make the disk copies. Later in the

day, tape copies are made. Backups under DMF took three hours during which no access could be made to the system. Backups were made only two times per week because of the system outage time.

NSL/UniTree's algorithm for purging files from the disk cache is not very flexible. Only one control is provided in the configuration files. Basically, one can choose to favor size or time. If one chooses to favor time, most files over one day old become equally likely to be purged. If one favors size, then a 500 MB file that is 30 minutes old will be purged before a 1 MB file that has not been accessed in five months. DMF allowed for a much more site-tunable purging algorithm.

DMF

- + Mature product with better tools and utilities.
- System outages cause denial of service.

NSL/UniTree

- Poor logs.
- + Shutting down system causes applications to block, not abort.
- + Faster backups allow for more frequent backups.
- Poor disk cache purging.
- No way to gracefully shutdown NSL/UniTree.

Stability

DMF proved to be a more stable product. It never crashed even when the system was very busy. Only on days of extreme activity (50,000 new files) did we have any problems. We would have to disable access to the system to allow DMF to catch up on migrations. Versions of NSL/UniTree prior to 2.1 were not stable enough for production use at LaRC. Version 2.1 has proven to be stable enough for our production use. However, it is less stable than DMF. On busy days we see a variety of problems including NSL/UniTree processes crashing and restarting. These restarts generally cause only a delay in service, although they sometimes result in minor database consistency problems. Also when the system is very active (more than 40-50 simultaneous I/O requests) we can get write I/O errors. Users then have to re-transfer the data.

Over the years we have had data loss due to events such as disk crashes and bad tapes, but have had no occurrences of data loss or corruption due to software bugs in either system in production use.

DMF

- + Very stable.

NSL/UniTree

- Less stable.

Performance

DMSS has provided better transfer rates than the CRAY Y-MP based solution. This improvement is seen by all clients from HIPPI-attached supercomputers to ethernet-attached workstations. The transfer rates have been between two and ten times better, depending on the situation.

NSL/UniTree suffers from poor file-access speeds (as mentioned earlier). Any applications that access (list, remove, and so on) even a moderate number of files see a performance penalty. DMF does not suffer the same problem. It gives typical UNIX file system response.

NSL/UniTree

- + Better file transfer rates.
- Poor file access performance.

Functionality

NSL/UniTree provides a number of useful features that DMF does not, including dynamic storage hierarchies, file families, and a file-by-file dual copy mechanism. Dynamic storage hierarchies allow the definition of any number of hierarchies consisting of many different devices. The hierarchy definitions tell NSL/UniTree how to migrate and cache files using the available devices. Each file can be assigned to any defined hierarchy by the user or the application. This feature allows a site and its users to better meet performance and cost requirements.

NSL/UniTree has the concept of file families, which allow files to be grouped together on tape. While this feature is nice, it allows only 32 families. This limits its usefulness to special requests and projects.

NSL/UniTree, like DMF, allows for multiple tape copies of a file to be written. NSL/UniTree is more flexible by allowing up to 16 copies of a file and allowing the user to specify the number of copies they want for each file.

NSL/UniTree

- + Extra features (especially dynamic storage hierarchies).

Conclusions

LaRC has placed a new cost-effective mass storage solution into production, which provides high availability and high-performance. The system is also flexible and scalable, allowing LaRC to better match user requirements with the appropriate level of service.

Comparing NSL/UniTree to DMF, we find that NSL/UniTree provides greater flexibility and functionality, but has some deficiencies (especially under heavy loads or when accessing large numbers of files). DMF is the more

mature product but lacks a number of features that affect availability and scalability.

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References

- [1] J. Pao and D. Humes, "NASA Langley Research Center's Distributed Mass Storage System," *Proc. 3rd NASA Goddard Conf. Mass Storage Systems and Technologies*, College Park, Oct. 1993.
- [2] S. Coleman and S. Miller, eds., "Mass Storage System Reference Model Version 4," *IEEE Technical Committee on Mass Storage Systems and Technology*, May 1990.
- [3] ISO/IEC, "Information Technology—Intelligent Peripheral Interface Part 3: Device Generic Command Set for Magnetic and Optical Disk Drives," ISO/IEC 9318-3, Sept. 1990.
- [4] R. Hyer, R. Ruef, and R. Watson, "High-Performance Data Transfer Using Network-Attached Peripherals at the National Storage Laboratory," *Proc. 12th IEEE Symp. Mass Storage Systems*, Monterey, April 1993.
- [5] ANSI, "High Performance Parallel Interface—Mechanical, Electrical and Signaling Protocol Specification (HIPPI-PH)," American Standards Institute, X3.183-1991.
- [6] ANSI, "High Performance Parallel Interface—Framing Protocol (HIPPI-FP) Preliminary Draft," American Standards Institute, X3.210-199x.
- [7] ANSI, "High Performance Parallel Interface—Physical Switch Control (HIPPI-SC)," American Standards Institute, X3.91-023-1991.
- [8] L. Buck et al., eds., "Mass Storage System Reference Model Version 5," *IEEE Storage Systems Standards Working Group*, Sept. 1994.